

The Effect of User Interface Design and User Experience Design on Consumers' Purchase Intentions of Shopee Application in Indonesia with Ease of Use as A Mediating Variable

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Abstract:

This study aimed to determine the effect of User Interface Design and User Experience Design on Perceived Ease of Use and Consumers' Purchase Intentions on the Shopee application, which is currently the first rank in e-commerce with the most monthly active users in Indonesia. As there are many users of the Shopee application, it is necessary to determine whether the design and ease of use affect consumers' purchase intentions. This research provided a novelty to the user interface design and user experience design constructs that used perceived ease of use as a mediating variable. The data collection method used a questionnaire with a total of 215 respondents through a purposive sampling technique. Using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with AMOS 26 tool, the results of this study indicated that User Interface Design and User Experience Design had a positive and significant effect on Perceived Ease of Use and Purchase Intention.

Keywords: *Perceived Ease of Use, Purchase Intention, Shopee, User Interface Design, User Experience Design*

1. Introduction

The development of e-commerce in Indonesia is very rapid; it has been recorded that the value of economic transactions in e-commerce during the first half of 2022 has reached IDR 227.8 trillion. This achievement experienced a growth of 22.1 percent compared to the same period in the previous year (Bank Indonesia). This increase is, of course, because, currently, consumers prefer transactions to buy goods or services online. One way to make transactions more accessible, especially in e-commerce, is to use an application. Shopee is one of the e-commerce that stands out in the Southeast Asian e-commerce market, including Indonesia; even the Shopee application ranks first in e-commerce with the most active monthly users in Indonesia (e-commerce, 2022). The presence of e-commerce in Indonesia has created intense competition. Intense competition makes e-commerce companies innovate and present attractive programs or features that can attract consumers' attention. One of the innovations made is to provide convenience in using the application.

The theory of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) explains the acceptance of technology use as one of the factors, namely perceived ease of use which Davis introduced (1989) as well as being a concept in this research. TAM is a model that can be modified or adapted to the results of the problem analysis. Perceived ease of use (perceived ease of use) is influenced by external variables related to the characteristics of a system that can increase the interest of technology users. The external variable is one part that can be modified in the TAM theory. Therefore, this study modified external variables using design variables.

User Interface Design is a space where the interaction between humans and technology itself, in other words, is an access point where users can understand the machine. At this time, User Interface Design is vital in digital products: websites, apps, screenshots, and more. The most complex User Interface Design will trigger a bad experience for the user. User Interface is often discussed in its relation to User Experience, which may include visual design, micro-interaction, layout design, and graphical user interfaces, resulting in content information being presented to the user within the context of the user interface (Interaction Design

Foundation, 2018).

In addition to User Interface Design, User Experience also plays an essential role in developing the customer experience in e-commerce and realizing that digital marketing can also trigger people to see the website or application itself, which will make users consider their purchase intentions. Youm & Yu (2013) explain that User Experience Design is a set of complex experiences and User Interface Designs in the minds of customer perceptions, which communicate expectations about the benefits that will be obtained from products produced by specific platforms. Through User Interface Design and User Experience Design, it is expected that it will make it easier for consumers to use an application. Massoud et al. (2018) found that perceived ease of use significantly influences purchase intention, which can increase sales of applications. Therefore, a better understanding of purchase intention is crucial for the effective use of e-commerce, especially to know the customer's perspective on Shopee e-commerce and to understand consumer behavior to improve the company's business. This research investigated the success of Shopee e-commerce from its ability to create users' purchase intention to shop online.

Several previous studies have identified several determinants of consumers' purchase intentions. Massoud et al. (2018); Tambunan et al. (2018); Arifah & Juniarti (2021); Pane et al. (2022) state that perceived ease of use has a significant effect on consumers' purchase intentions, whereas JDachyar & Banjarnahor (2017) state that perceived ease of use does not support consumers' purchase intentions. Further research was also carried out by Wuryandari et al. (2019) stated that User Interface Design has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention. In contrast, research conducted by Watulingas & Permana (2020) states that User Interface has no, but a significant effect on purchase intention, as well as in a study conducted by Arifah & Juniarti (2021), Interface Aesthetic also has no effect on consumers' purchase intentions. Furthermore, research conducted by Watulingas & Permana (2020) also states that User Experience has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention. In contrast, according to Wuryandari et al. (2019), User Experience has no effect on consumers' intention to buy. Therefore, from the several gaps in the analysis, we aim to examine whether these factors influence the purchase intention of Shopee application consumers. Also, to the best of our knowledge, there has been no literature study using perceived ease of use as a mediating variable to explore the design component of purchase intention, presented as a new model in this study. Thus, this study aims to determine the factors that influence consumers' purchase intentions on e-commerce websites by using the variables; User Interface Design and User Experience Design, as well as Perceived Ease of Use as a mediating variable.

2. Literature review

2.1 User Interface Design

User interface design can be interpreted as the design/display of the application interface for users. The User Interface is the initial application design that is accessed directly for the first time when the user will make a transaction on a system. Website design is the navigation scheme and hierarchy used on a website along with its visual design, such as visual appeal, innovation, aesthetics, and the use of colors and shapes (Dedeke, 2016). Website design is even bigger in online purchases than the services provided to customers in traditional stores (Hasan, 2016).

2.2 User Experience Design

Design User Experience is one of the most critical components in e-commerce that functions to meet customers' needs appropriately (Vavliakis et al., 2019). Design User Experience includes all emotions, beliefs, preferences, perceptions, physical and psychological responses, behaviors, and achievements before, during, and after using something (Muslim et al., 2019). Good responses and ratings from users regarding User Experience Design can be an attraction for potential new users to use digital business products (Fitriana & Yanto, 2020). Furthermore, the responses and ratings from these users can be used as feedback for businesses to be able to design systems that are even better and make it easier for users to interact with applications.

2.3 Perceived Ease of Use

Perceived ease of use is defined as people believing that using certain technologies will be free of effort (Davis, 1989). According to Childers (2001), online businesses that provide clear and easy-to-

understand information with minimal effort and enable consumers to shop the way they want to generate perceptions of ease of use in the minds of consumers with favorable attitude attachments to online. Selamat et al. (2009) argue that consumers always accept easier technology than using complex technology.

2.4 Purchase Intention

Based on Kotler and Keller (2009), consumers' purchase intention is a consumer behavior in which consumers have the desire to buy or choose a product based on their experience in selecting, using and consuming, or even wanting a product. An individual intending to buy a product shows a higher level of actual purchase compared to a customer with no intention to buy. Purchase intention is a condition between the customer and the seller when the customer is ready to agree with the seller (Raza et al., 2014). Purchase intention is defined as a decision to act or a mental stage in the decision-making process where consumers have developed an actual willingness to act toward an object or brand (Wang & Yang, 2008; Wells, Valacich & Hess, 2011).

3. Empirical Model & Hypothesis

3.1 User Interface Design – Perceived Ease of Use

User interface design refers to the design of the structural interface design that displays the features that support an information system. The quality of the user interface determines the level of users' perceived ease of use, so it must be considered in system development. According to previous research showing User Interface Design has an impact on perceived ease of use (Rasidi et al., 2021). Previous research has also shown a positive relationship between Web Interface Quality and the Perceived ease of shopping online (Vu et al., 2020). Thus the hypothesis proposed is as follows:

H1: User Interface Design has an impact on the perceived ease of use

3.2 User Experience Design - Perceived Ease of Use

User experience is one of the most critical components in e-commerce that functions to meet customers' needs appropriately (Vavliakis et al., 2019). According to previous research, user experience has an effect on perceived ease of use (Syed-Abdul et al., 2019). Previous research also shows that User Experience (UX) has a significant positive direct effect on Perceived Ease Of Use (PEOU) (Santoso & Wiradinata, 2014). Thus, the hypothesis proposed is as follows:

H2: User Experience Design has an impact on the perceived ease of use

3.3 Perceived Ease of Use – Purchase Intention

Perceived Ease of Use refers to the extent to which users perceive certain technologies, access websites, Internet functions, and application interfaces are easy to use (Davis, 1989). In other words, the easier a technology application is, the more likely it will be used to increase sales in e-commerce applications. Moslehpour et al. (2018) state that Perceived Ease Of Use has a significant influence on Purchase Intention. Therefore, a technology considered easy to use will stimulate customers to buy online. In addition, Childers et al. (2001) argue that clear and understandable online shopping sites, which require less mental effort to make a purchase, are more attractive to potential customers than more complex ones. This finding is significant because online shoppers reveal that the ease of the website, which is free of effort to place an order, is part of the main factor for the success of virtual stores. Thus, the hypothesis proposed is as follows:

H3: Perceived ease of use has an impact on the Purchase Intention

3.4 User Interface Design - Purchase Intention

User Interface Design can be defined as the first impression the user encounters. This variable may be one of the reasons every user uses the product. In other words, User Interface Design to Purchase Intention is a tendency that determines the acceptance of user feedback. Individuals always speculate that good design can trigger their Purchase Intention, making Purchase Intention depend on a good User Interface, which includes Visual Design, Micro-Interaction, and design layout (Youm & Yu, 2013). Previous research also has shown that the User Interface has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Intention (Watulingas & Permana, 2020). Other research has also found that the User Interface Design variable has a positive and

significant effect on Purchase Intention (Wuryandari et al., 2019). Thus the hypothesis proposed is as follows:

H4: User Interface Design has an impact on the Purchase Intention

3.5 User Experience Design - Purchase Intention

User Experience Design is usability and other components related to the experience of using the product. One reason is how people interact with the design itself, including; how the design communicates with the user and how it flows until the user meets their expectations. Meanwhile, suppose the user experience cannot meet the user's expectations. In that case, they will most likely be lost because once they feel uncomfortable using an application, website, or other digital product, dissatisfaction will be the first thing that comes to mind. In other words, if the website or application has a good experience, the product can stand out so that users will consider exploring rather than increasing purchase intentions (Vandecandelaere, 2018). Previous research has also found that User Experience had a positive and significant effect on Purchase Intention (Watulingas & Permana, 2020). Thus the hypothesis proposed is as follows:

H5: User Experience Design has an impact on the Purchase Intention

3.6 User Interface Design – User Experience Design - Perceived Ease of Use - Purchase Intention

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) theory (Davis, 1989) shows the relationship between external variable constructs will have a direct influence on the perceived ease of use construct. The perceived ease of use construct is influenced by external variables related to the characteristics of a system that can increase the interest of technology users. One of these external variables is the design of the technology, such as the design of the application. Through User Interface design and User Experience design, it is hoped that it will make it easier for consumers to use an Application. According to Massoud et al., 2018 perceived ease of use significantly affects purchase intentions. Thus, it can increase sales of an application. Therefore, the hypothesis proposed is as follows:

H6: Perceived Ease of Use mediates the impact between User Interface Design and Purchase Intention

H7: Perceived Ease of Use mediates the impact between User Experience Design and Purchase Intention

4. Methodology

4.1 Measurements

Causal research was the design chosen in this study. This study used a questionnaire distributed to respondents considered to meet predetermined criteria. The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree). User Interface Design was measured based on five indicators developed by Schlatter (2013). Furthermore, to measure User Experience Design, it used the UX Honeycomb theory developed by Morville (2004). In addition, measuring Perceived Ease of Use used five indicators developed by Davis et al. (1989) and Jimenez et al. (2016). As for measuring purchase intention, it used a combination of five indicators developed by Veno et al. (2019); Pepper et al. (2009); Amin et al. (2011); (Noor, 2013) with a total of 21 indicators. Information regarding the demographic characteristics of the respondents was conveyed regarding the gender of the respondent, the age of the respondent, the respondent's domicile, the respondent's occupation, and when they last used the Shopee Application.

4.2 Sampling and Data Collection

The number of samples collected and studied in this study was 215 respondents. The samples involved were Shopee Application users who were domiciled in Indonesia and had used the Shopee Application for less than 1 year. Sampling locations were distributed in various cities in Indonesia, such as Jakarta, Bandung, Medan, Surabaya, Semarang, Samarinda, Banjarmasin, Makassar, Pontianak, and various other regions of Indonesia, through online questionnaires.

4.3 Data Analysis

This research used Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with the AMOS 26 statistical tool to analyze and evaluate the measurement model and structural model of the research construct that was built. The model fit test was assessed based on goodness of fit index parameters such as goodness of fit index (GFI),

Tucker Lewis Index (TLI), Incremental Fit Index (IFI), Comparative Fit Index (CFI), and Normal Fit Index (NFI). The validity evaluation relied on the standardized loading factor (SLF) value, which must be ≥ 0.50 (Hair et al., 2014: 618), and the reliability constructs relied on the tabulated results of construct reliability (CR) and average variance extracted (AVE) values. Furthermore, the SEM analysis carried out was a structural model analysis to assess the research hypothesis that had been built and whether it was accepted or rejected. SEM analysis displayed the t-value for each coefficient. The hypothesis could be said to have a causal relationship if the t-count value $\geq t$ table (1.96) with a significant level of α (usually $\alpha = 0.05$).

Results and Discussions

5.1 Respondent Characteristics

The analysis of the respondents' profiles in this research was based on the following demographic characteristics:

Table 1. Characteristics of Respondents

Category	Item	f	%
Gender	Male	77	35.8
	Female	138	64.2
	Total	215	100
Age	15-19 years old	30	14
	20-29 years old	165	76.7
	30-39 years old	16	7.4
	40-45 years old	4	1.9
	Total	215	100
Domicile	Pontianak	97	45.2
	Jakarta	25	11.6
	Bandung	8	3.7
	Bogor	14	6.5
	Surabaya	14	6.5
	Malang	8	3.7
	Semarang	11	5.1
	Yogyakarta	13	6
	Makassar	4	1.9
	Others	21	9.8
Total	215	100	
Jobs	Student/University Student	137	63.8
	Civil Servants	8	3.7
	Private	25	11.6
	Entrepreneur	15	7
	Freelance	28	13
	Others	2	0.9
	Total	215	100
Last used the Shopee Application	< 1 week ago	143	66.6
	< 1 month ago	52	24.2
	< 3 months ago	16	7.4
	< 6 months ago	2	0.9
	< 1 year ago	2	0.9
Total	215	100	

Table 1 is the result of the data from respondents who filled out the research questionnaire. Women dominated the gender category in the respondent data for this study, and the age category was dominated in the range of 20-29 years. Pontianak also dominated the city category with a percentage of 45%, while the job category was dominated by students or university students. Also, 66.6% of respondents used the Shopee

application for less than one week.

5.2 Measurement and Structural Models

Results related to validity and reliability tests, as well as the goodness of fit, can be presented as follows:

Table 2. Measurement Model Results

Items		SLF	CR	AVE
User Interface Design	Shopee application can show its characteristics	0.926	0.9946	0.837
	The layout of the Shopee application is easy to understand	0.908		
	The layout of the Shopee application is well structured	0.923		
	The color design of the Shopee application is attractive	0.912		
	The use of pictures on the Shopee application is attractive	0.905		
User Experience Design	The Shopee application is useful to me	0.926	0.9952	0.826
	The Shopee application can help my activities	0.918		
	The Shopee application is fun to use	0.911		
	The Shopee application is the application I need	0.918		
	It is easy to find the product I need on the Shopee application	0.893		
	I trust the Shopee app when I provide my data	0.885		
Perceived Ease of Use	The Shopee application is easy to use	0.886	0.9955	0.793
	This Shopee application is understandable	0.895		
	The Shopee application is easy to learn	0.912		
	The Shopee application is easy to obtain	0.89		
	The Shopee application is easily accessible	0.869		
Purchase Intention	I intend to buy on the Shopee Application	0.874	0.9952	0.771
	Shopee application is interesting to use for product shopping	0.88		
	I will purchase products in the future	0.875		
	I will recommend other people to buy products on the Shopee Application	0.873		
	The Shopee application makes it easy to communicate with shop owners	0.888		

Table 2 is the result of testing the validity and reliability of the overall model. The standardized loading factor (SLF) value of all indicator variables in the full model had a value above 0.50. It means that all indicators were declared valid and believed to be able to measure the construct of the full model being built. The results of the reliability test presented appropriate results. All instruments were declared reliable and had the ability to measure the constructs of the full model built consistently. It is shown from the average variance extracted (AVE) value of all instrument indicators, which obtained a value of ≥ 0.50 , and the value of construct reliability (CR) which obtained a value of ≥ 0.70

Table 3. The goodness of Fit Index

The goodness of Fit Index	Cut off Value	Results
TLI	≥ 0.90	0.917
IFI	≥ 0.90	0.927
CFI	≥ 0.90	0.927
NFI	≥ 0.90	0.905

Table 3 is the result of the model fit test. The model fit test results show that the model fit

requirements could be accepted and declared fit. There were four measurements that indicated the degree of good fit. Hair et al. (2014: 583) state that a research model construct can be declared fit and accepted if there are three to four measurements that obtain a degree of good fit or above the cut-off value.

5.2.1 Hypotheses Testing

Fig 1: Full Model Structural Test

Based on figure 1, table 4, the t-score value of User Interface Design on Perceived Ease of Use was 7.428, greater than the t-table value (1.96). Likewise, the p-value was less than 0.001, less than 0.05 ($\alpha = 0.05$). These results were related to the first hypothesis, where User Interface Design had a positive and significant effect on Perceived Ease of Use. In the second hypothesis, the t-score value of User Experience Design on Perceived Ease of Use was 9.09, and the p-value was less than 0.001; less than 0.05 ($\alpha = 0.05$). This proves that User Experience Design had a positive and significant effect on Perceived Ease of Use. In the third hypothesis, the t-value of Perceived Ease of Use on Purchase Intention was 3.413, and the p-value was less than 0.001; less than 0.05 ($\alpha = 0.05$). Thus, Perceived Ease of Use had a positive and significant effect on Purchase Intention on the Shopee Application. In the fourth hypothesis, the t-score value of User Interface Design on Purchase Intention was 2.681, greater than the t-table value (1.96). Likewise, the p-value was 0.007; less than 0.05 ($\alpha = 0.05$), then the User Interface Design had a positive and significant effect on Purchase Intention. In the fifth hypothesis, the t-score value of User Experience Design on Purchase Intention was 3.873, and the p-value was less than 0.001; less than 0.05 ($\alpha = 0.05$). This proves that User Experience Design had a positive and significant effect on Purchase Intention.

Table 4. Hypothesis Testing

Item	Std Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Description
UID --> PEOU	0.465	0.062	7.482	***	Accepted
UXD --> PEOU	0.599	0.066	9.09	***	Accepted
PEOU --> PI	0.445	0.13	3.413	***	Accepted
UID --> PI	0.204	0.076	2.681	0.007	Accepted
UXD --> PI	0.362	0.093	3.873	***	Accepted

Table 5. Sobel Test – Significance of Mediation

Item	Sobel Test Statistic	Two-tailed Probability	Description
UID --> PEOU --> PI	3.091	0.0019	Accepted
UXD --> PEOU --> PI	3.172	0.0015	Accepted

Based on the Sobel test results in table 5, it can be seen that the statistical value of the Sobel test was 3.091 and 3.172, and the p-value was 0.001. The results show that the Sobel test value was greater than the t-table (1.96). Likewise, the p-value obtained was smaller than 0.05 ($\alpha = 0.05$). It shows a significant and positive indirect effect of the User Interface Design and User Experience Design variables on Purchase Intention through Perceived Ease of Use. The results of this study were in line with previous research with the Theory of Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1989), indicating that the relationship between external variable constructs would have a direct influence on the perceived ease of use constructs. The perceived ease of use construct was influenced by external variables related to the characteristics of a system that could increase the interest of technology users. One of these external variables was the design of the technology, such as the design of the application. Through User Interface and User Experience design, it is hoped that it would make it easier for consumers to use an application. Moslehpour et al. (2018) state that perceived ease of use significantly affects purchase intentions. Thus, this can increase sales of an application.

5. Discussion

The results of the Sobel test show that user interface design and user experience design have a positive and significant effect on consumers' purchase intentions, with perceived ease of use as a mediating variable driving consumers' purchase intention of the Shopee application. This finding is supported by the TAM theory, which shows the relationship between external variable constructs will have a direct influence on the perceived ease of use construct. The perceived ease of use construct is influenced by external variables related to the characteristics of a system that can increase the interest of technology users. One of these external variables is the design of the technology, such as the design of the application. In this study, User Interface Design and User Experience proved to have a positive and significant effect on perceived ease of use in the Shopee application, which is supported by previous research showing that User Interface Design has an impact on perceived ease of use Rashidi et al. (2021). Previous research has also shown a positive relationship between Web Interface Quality and the Perceived ease of shopping online (Vu et al., 2020). Also, User experience influences Perceived ease of use (Syed-Abdul et al., 2019).

Previous research has also shown that User Experience (UX) has a significant positive direct effect on Perceived Ease Of Use (PEOU) (Santoso & Wiradinata, 2014). The ease of use of the Shopee application will also affect consumers' purchase intentions, as proven in this study. It is also supported by previous research, which has found that perceived ease of use significantly influences purchase intention. (Moslehpour et al., 2018); (Arifah & Juniarti, 2021) ; (Pane et al., 2022). This research also shows that user interface design and user experience design have a positive and significant effect on consumers' purchase intentions for the Shopee application. It is supported by previous research, which shows that the User Interface has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Intention (Watulingas & Permana, 2020); (Wuryandari et al., 2019). In addition, User Experience has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Intention (Watulingas & Permana, 2020).

6. Conclusion

The intense competition in e-commerce today forces e-commerce companies to always innovate and present attractive programs or features that can attract consumers' attention. The effect of user interface design and user experience design on ease of use shows that Shopee consumers feel these two designs can make it easier for them to use the Shopee application. Hence, the Shopee application management must continue to develop application designs that make it easier to use. In addition, the ease of use affects consumers' purchase intentions so that it can increase sales. User interface design and user experience design also influence consumers' purchase intentions, so besides being able to facilitate use, this design can also influence consumers' purchase intentions. From this study, it can be concluded that user interface design and user experience design are essential to increase sales in e-commerce, especially in the Shopee application. Therefore, this research provides an overview of the management of the Shopee application that needs to improve the design to make it easier for consumers to use the Shopee application so that it can also increase consumers' purchase intentions on the Shopee application. As well as for other e-commerce, this research can also provide information and references to increase purchases on e-commerce.

7. Limitations and Future Research

In this study, the sample used was dominated by students or university students with an age range also dominated by 20-29 years. Therefore, it was not sufficient to represent other age ranges. Furthermore, this research was only conducted on consumers of the Shopee application and used the variables; User Interface Design, User Experience Design, Perceived Ease of Use, and Purchase Intentions. Future research can take a broader sample and other variables that can influence consumers' purchase intentions. The results of this study are expected to become literature and references to develop more in-depth research on consumers' purchase intentions.

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